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In-Vitro and In-Vivo Anti-Inflammatory Activity of Leaves Extract of *Kalanchoe pinnata* Plant

Gangadhar Yadav¹, Bishan poudel², Avrak Hamal³, S.M.Bhatt⁴, Sanjay Raj baral⁵

¹ School of Pharmacy Chitwan Medical College, Bharatpur-5, Chitwan, Nepal

^{2,3} Amritsar Group Of Colleges, Amritsar, Punjab, India

⁴ Department of Biotechnology, IIMT University, Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, India

⁵ Assistant professor, Chitwan Medical College, TU

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the present study was to evaluate the in-vitro and in-vivo anti-inflammatory activity of aqueous and ethanolic leaf extract of the *Kalanchoe pinnata* plant. Aqueous and ethanolic extract of the leaves was prepared by cold maceration. The anti-inflammatory activities of the aqueous and ethanolic extracts of the leaves were performed by both in vitro and in vivo methods. The in vitro method was estimated by the human red blood cell membrane stabilization (HRBC) method and the in vivo method was estimated on the carrageenan-induced paw edema. Data were analyzed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Dunnett's t-test was used as the test of significance. P-value <0.05 was considered as the minimum level of significance. The data revealed that varying concentrations of aqueous and ethanolic *Kalanchoe pinnata* plant significantly stabilized erythrocyte membrane against hypotonicity-induced hemolysis in a dose-dependent manner. Similarly, the plant extracts showed significant anti-inflammatory activity in dose dose-dependent manner in the carrageenan-induced paw edema model. The inhibition of paw edema was found to be 86.38% for diclofenac 10mg/kg, 67.91% for ethanolic extract (300mg/kg), 71.52% for ethanolic extract (600mg/kg), 68.61% for aqueous extract (300mg/kg) and 83.75% for aqueous extract 600mg/kg maximally. Among the extracts, aqueous extract showed more inhibitory activity on inflammation. The results of the present study demonstrate that aqueous and ethanolic leaf extract of *kalanchoe pinnata* possesses significant (P < 0.05) anti-inflammatory activity.

Keywords: Anti-Inflammatory Activity, *Kalanchoe pinnata* (Lam.) Pers, human red blood cell membrane stabilization, paw-edema

1. Introduction:

The *Kalanchoe* species is extensively used in complementary and alternative therapy¹. It is one of the Pashanbhed (meaning stone breaker) plants mentioned in ancient Ayurvedic literature. *Kalanchoe pinnata* (Lam.) Pers (synonyms *Bryophyllum calycinum*, *Bryophyllum pinnatum*) belong to the family *Crassulaceae* and is commonly known as life plant, cathedral bells, air plant (Mexican), love plant, Canterbury, patharchatta (Nepali) etc⁴. It is a perennial herb growing widely and used in folkloric medicine in tropical India, China, Austria, Nepal, and tropical America⁶.

Figure 1 *Kalanchoe pinnata* plant

Kalanchoe pinnata contains a wide range of active compounds, including alkaloids, triterpenes, glycosides, flavonoids, steroids, bufadienolides, lipids, and organic acids³⁴. The *Kalanchoe pinnata* (Lam.) Pers is widely used in the Ayurvedic system of medicine as an analgesic, astringent, and carminative and is also useful in diarrhea and vomiting². *Kalanchoe pinnata* (Lam.) Pers has many pharmacological properties such as anti-diabetic, antimicrobial, anticancer, insecticidal, and anti-urolithiatic etc⁵. The plant leaves are used as ethno medicine traditionally³. It is used for wound healing and anti-inflammatory activity³⁵.

Inflammation is a response triggered by damage to living tissues³⁶. The inflammatory response is a defense mechanism that evolved in higher organisms to protect them from infection and injury³⁷. Its purpose is to localize and eliminate the injurious agent and to remove damaged tissue components so that the body can begin to heal³⁸. The response consists of changes in blood flow, an increase in the permeability of blood vessels, and the migration of fluid, proteins, and white blood cells (leukocytes) from the circulation to the site of tissue damage. An inflammatory response that lasts only a few days is called acute inflammation, while a response of longer duration is referred to as chronic inflammation³⁹. A drug or substance that reduces inflammation (redness, swelling, and pain) in the body is called an anti-inflammatory drug or substance. Antiinflammatory agents block certain substances in the body that cause inflammation¹².

The main mechanism of action of anti-inflammatory drugs is the inhibition of the enzyme cyclooxygenase (COX). Cyclooxygenase is required to convert arachidonic acid into thromboxanes, prostaglandins, and prostacyclins. The therapeutic effects of anti-inflammatory drugs are attributed to the lack of these eicosanoids. Specifically, thromboxanes play a role in platelet adhesion; prostaglandins cause vasodilation, increase the temperature set-point in the hypothalamus, and play a role in anti-nociception.

There are two cyclooxygenase isoenzymes, COX-1 and COX-2. COX-1 gets constitutively expressed in the body, and it plays a role in maintaining gastrointestinal mucosa lining, kidney function, and platelet aggregation. COX-2 is not constitutively expressed in the body; instead, it is inducibly expressed during an inflammatory response. Most of the anti-inflammatory drugs are nonselective and inhibit both COX-1 and COX-2.

However, COX-2 selective antiinflammatory drugs only target COX-2 and therefore have a different side effect profile. Importantly, because COX-1 is the prime mediator for ensuring gastric mucosal integrity and COX-2 is mainly involved in inflammation; COX-2 selective anti-inflammatory drugs should provide anti-inflammatory relief without compromising the gastric mucosa⁴².

In vitro is Latin for “in glass.” It describes medical procedures, tests, and experiments that researchers perform outside of a living organism. An in vitro study occurs in a controlled environment, such as a test tube or petri dish¹⁵. In vivo is Latin for “within the living.” It refers to tests, experiments, and procedures that researchers perform in or on a whole living organism, such as a person, laboratory animal, or plant¹⁷.

2. Material and Methods

The entire study was carried out in the Department of Pharmacy and Biochemistry laboratory of Chitwan Medical College. The extraction procedure, phytochemical screening, and in-vivo anti-inflammatory activity were performed in the Pharmacy laboratory whereas in-vitro anti-inflammatory activity was performed in the Biochemistry laboratory of Chitwan Medical College with the approval of the Head of Department of respective department.

2.1 Sample collection and identification

The leaves of *Kalanchoe pinnata* were collected from the locality of Rajpur, Dang district, and were identified by botanists from Rampur Agricultural and Forestry University. The herbarium of the leaves was prepared and preserved in the lab of the pharmacy department. The leaves of patharchatta were washed and shade-dried for 30 days at room temperature, and mechanically pulverized. Then it was preserved in a container away from light, heat, and moisture for later use.

2.2 Preparation of leaf extract

Extraction was carried out by cold maceration process. Dried leaves of 100g were soaked with 500ml of ethanol (95% v/v) and distilled water for 3 days by using a cold maceration process with occasionally shaken. After 3 days, both the ethanolic and aqueous extracts were filtered using Whatmann no.1 filter paper. The solvent was further dried out by using a rotary evaporator and obtained concentrated extracts were subjected to a vacuum desiccator. Extractive value was calculated. The resultant dried extracts were used for further study¹⁵.

2.3 Phytochemical screening of leaves extract

The phytochemical screening was done to detect the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, tannins, and carbohydrates using standard test procedure³.

2.3.1 Test for alkaloids:

a. Mayer's reagent test: Mayer's reagent was used to test alkaloids. 2ml of botanical extract was taken in a test tube and 2-3 drops of Mayer's reagent were added to it. The presence of alkaloids was indicated by the appearance of a creamy white color precipitate in the solution.

b. Wager's test: Wagner's test was done by using Wagner's reagent. When a few drops of Wagner's reagent were added to the test tube containing 2ml of extract, the appearance of brick color precipitate indicated the presence of alkaloids.

2.3.2 Test for flavonoids:

a) Alkaline reagent test: In the alkaline reagent test, 2ml of botanicals were taken in a test tube and 2ml of sodium hydroxide (2% w/v) solution was also added to it. An intense yellow color appeared in the test tube. In addition to a few drops of dilute hydrochloric acid, it was colorless which indicated the presence of flavonoids.

b) Lead acetate test: In the lead acetate test 1ml of the extract was taken in the test tube and a few drops (3-4 drops) of 10% solution was added to it then yellow precipitate was formed which indicated the presence of flavonoids.

2.3.3 Test for tannins:

a) Test for Polyphenols and Tannins Crude extract was mixed with 2ml of 2% solution of FeCl₃. A blue-green or blue-black coloration indicated the presence of polyphenols and tannins.

2.3.4 Test for Steroids:

a) Crude extract was mixed with 2ml of chloroform and concentrated H₂SO₄ was added sidewise. A red color produced in the lower chloroform layer indicates the presence of steroids. Another test was performed by mixing

the crude extract with 2ml of chloroform. Then 2ml of each of concentrated H_2SO_4 and acetic acid was poured into the mixture. The development of a greenish coloration indicates the presence of steroids.

2.3.5 Test for Reducing Sugars:

a) In the reducing sugar test, 2ml of an ethanolic extract of the plant material was added to 1ml of a mixture of equal volume of Fehling's solution A & B and was boiled for 5 minutes in a boiling water bath. The formation of a brick-red color precipitate shows the presence of reducing sugars.

2.3.6 Test for Gums:

a) For the gum test 5ml of the extract was taken and then Molisch's reagent and sulphuric acid were added. The formation of a red-violet ring at the junction of two liquids indicates the presence of gums.

2.3.7 Test for carbohydrates:

a) Molisch's test: The 2ml of sample solution was taken in a clean test tube. Added 2-3 drops of Molisch's reagent slowly and mixed well then added conc. Sulfuric acid along the side of the test tube. The violet ring was formed at the junction of the two layers which indicated the presence of carbohydrates.

b) Benedict's test: First take 5ml of Benedict solution in a clean test tube then add exactly 8 drops of extract solution on it. The mixing solution was boiled for 2 minutes then a green precipitate was formed which indicated the presence of reducing sugar.

2.3.8 Test for Glycosides:

a. A small amount of ethanolic or aqueous extract was taken in 1ml of water in a test tube and a few drops of aqueous NaOH were added. A yellow coloration indicates the presence of glycosides.

b. Keller-Kiliani Test: A solution of glacial acetic acid (4.0 ml) with 1 drop of 2% $FeCl_3$ mixture was mixed with the 10ml aqueous or ethanolic plant extract and 1ml H_2SO_4 concentrated. A brown ring formed between the layers which showed the entity of cardiac steroidal glycosides.

c. Salkowski's Test: firstly added 2ml H_2SO_4 concentrated to the aqueous plant crude extract. A reddish brown color formed which indicated the presence of steroidal aglycone part of the glycoside.

2.3.9 Test for Saponins

a) Foam test: The extract solution was diluted with distilled water and taken in a test tube. There was a suspension formed for minutes. A cm layer of foam indicated the presence of saponins.

2.4 Experimental animals

Male albino rats weighing 150-200g and of approximately the same age were used in the study. These animals were procured from Godawari Botanical Garden, Kathmandu. The animals were fed with a standard pellet diet and water. All the animals were housed in polypropylene cages. The animals were kept under alternate cycles of 12 hours of darkness and light at 25 ± 2 °C. The animals were acclimatized to the laboratory conditions for 1 week before starting the experiment. The animals were fasted for at least 12 hours before the onset of each activity. The experimental protocols were approved by CMC-IRC. The drug treatment was given to the animals by oral gavage tube.

2.5 Evaluation of anti-inflammatory activity:

2.5.1 In-vitro method:

The human red blood cell (HRBC) membrane stabilization method: A blood sample (5ml) was collected from a human volunteer for the experiment. For the experiment, human volunteers did not consume NSAIDs for 2 weeks at least the experiment. The blood sample was mixed with an equal volume of Alsever solution (2% dextrose, 0.8% sodium citrate, 0.5% citric acid, and 0.42% NaCl) and was centrifuged at 3,000 rpm for 10min; the supernatant was removed and the packed cells obtained was washed with isosaline solution (0.9%, pH 7.2) and a 10% suspension was made. Various concentrations of extracts were prepared (200 and 400 µg/ml) using distilled water and to each concentration, 1 ml of phosphate buffer, 2ml hyposaline (0.36%), and 0.5 ml of HRBC suspension were added. The samples were incubated at 37°C for 30 min and were further centrifuged at 3,000 rpm for 20 min. The hemoglobin content of the supernatant solution was estimated by using UV- a visible spectrophotometer at wavelength 560 nm. Diclofenac (100 and 200 µg/ml) was used as reference standard. Control was prepared without using extracts and instead of the hyposaline, 2ml distilled water was used. The percentage of HRBC membrane stabilization or protection was calculated by using the following Formula¹⁸:

$$\% \text{ protection} = 100 - \frac{\text{optical density of drug-treated sample} \times 100\%}{\text{the optical density of control}}$$

2.5.2 In-vivo method:

Table 1

TREATMENT DESIGN:	
Group-I	Normal Control (Carrageen 1%w/v).
Group-II	Positive control (diclofenac 10mg/kg).
Group- III	Ethanolic extract (300mg/kg).
Group-IV	Ethanolic extract (600mg/kg).
Group-V	Aqueous extract (300mg/kg).
Group-VI	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg) ¹⁵ .

A carrageenan-induced paw edema inflammation model in rats was used to evaluate the anti-inflammatory activity of the leaf extract of *Kalanchoe pinnata*¹⁵ Male albino rats weighing between 150-200 grams was divided into 6 groups as group-I normal control, group-II positive control, group-III ethanolic extract (300mg/kg), group-IV ethanolic extract (600mg/kg), group-V aqueous extract (300mg/kg) and group-VI aqueous extract (600mg/kg) & each group consist 5 rats. The different groups were treated as shown in the design table. Acute inflammation was produced in rats in the entire group by the subplantar administration of 0.1ml carrageenan (1%) [which was prepared in normal saline] in the left paw of rats. The paw volume was measured at 0, 30, 60, 120, and 180 minutes after carrageenan injection using the digital vernier caliper. The animals of groups III and IV were pretreated with ethanolic extracts and V, and VI with aqueous extracts 60 minutes before the administration of Carrageenan. The inhibition of swelling was compared with that of the control group¹⁵.

The % inhibition of paw-edema was calculated by:

$$\% \text{ inhibition of paw-edema} = \frac{(C-T) \times 100}{C}$$

Where:

C= Increase in paw volume of the control group.

T= Increase in paw volume after administration of extracts.

2.6 Statistical analysis:

The data was analyzed using the IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 20 for Windows. The experimental results were expressed as Mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM), and statistical significance was determined by employing a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Dunnet's T-test. The level of significance was $p < 0.05$.

2.7 Ethical consideration

Ethical approval was taken from CMC-IRC (Institutional Review Committee no.036). Lab work was performed in compliance with GLP (good laboratory practice) and experimental procedure was carried out following Ethical Guidelines for the Care and Use of Animals in Health Research in Nepal 2005.

3. Results

3.1 Phytochemical screening of aqueous and ethanolic extract of *Kalanchoe pinnata* plant

3.1.1 Extractive value of Crude Drug

- Weight of Powder of *Kalanchoe pinnata* taken = 280 gm
- Weight of dried extract = 12.18 gm
- 280 gm of the dried drug gives 12.18 gm of aqueous soluble extract
- 100 gm of dried drug gives 4.35 gm of aqueous soluble extract
- The aqueous soluble extractive value of crude drug of leaves of *Kalanchoe pinnata* was found to be 4.35% w/w
- Weight of Powdered *Kalanchoe pinnata* taken = 280 gm
- Weight of dried extract = 9.35 gm
- 280 gm of the dried drug gives 9.35 gm of ethanolic soluble extract
- 100 gm of the dried drug gives 3.3392 gm of ethanolic soluble extract
- The ethanolic soluble extractive value of crude drug of leaves of *Kalanchoe pinnata* was found to be 3.3392% w/w.

3.1.2 Preliminary phytochemical screening

Preliminary phytochemical screening of ethanolic and aqueous extracts of *K.Pinnata* showed the presence of Steroids, Saponins, Alkaloids, Glycosides, Flavonoids, Carbohydrate, Gum, reducing sugar and Tannins. The results are expressed in table 2.

Table 2 Preliminary phytochemical screening of ethanolic and aqueous extracts of *K.Pinnata*.

S.N	Phytochemical	Test	Observation	Ethanollic extract	Aqueous extract	Inference
1	Alkaloids	a) Mayer's test (Few mL filtrates + 1-2 drops of Mayer's reagent. Along the sides of the test tube)	Yellow /creamy white color precipitate	+	+	_ =absent +=presence
		b) Wagner's test (Few mL filtrate + 1-2 drops of Wagner's reagent)	brown/reddish precipitate	+	+	_ =absent +=presence
2	Flavonoids	a) Lead acetate test (1mL plant extract + few drops of 10% lead acetate solution)	yellow color	+	+	_ =absent +=presence
		b) Alkaline reagent test (1mL extract + 2mL of 2% NaOH solution (+ few drops dil. HCl))	An intense yellow color becomes colorless with the addition of diluted acid	+	+	_ =absent +=presence
3	Phenols	a) Ferric chloride test (Extract aqueous solution + few drops 10% ferric chloride solution)	Bluish-green color	+	+	_ =absent
4	Tannins	b) Braymer's test (1mL filtrated)	Bluish color	-	+	_ =absent +=presence

5	Carbohydrates	a) Molisch's test (2mL filtrate + 2 drops of alcoholic α -naphthol + 1mL conc. H_2SO_4 , along the sides of the test).	Purple ring	+	+	_ =absent
		b) Benedict's test (8 drops exact filtrate + 5mL. Benedict's reagent + Boiled for 2 min).	Green color	+	+	_ =absent
6	Glycoside	a) Keller-killani test (1mL filtrate + 1.5mL glacial acetic acid + 1 drop of 5% ferric chloride) +	A brown ring solution (in acetic acid)	-	+	_ =absent +=presence
		Conc. H_2SO_4 (along the side of the test tube)				
		b) Salkowski's test (Filtrate + few drops of conc. H_2SO_4)	Reddish colour	+	+	_ =absent +=presence
7	Gum	Extract + molisch's reagent + sulphuric acid	Violet ring	+	+	_ =absent

8	Reducing sugar	Fehling's test (1mL each of Fehling's solution A & B + 1mL filtrated + boiled in water bath)	A red precipitated	+	+	_ =absent +=presence
9	Saponins	The extract was diluted with distilled water and the foam was measured	Foam formed	+	-	_ =absent +=presence

3.2 In-vitro anti-inflammatory activity

The in vitro anti-inflammatory activity of the extracts was concentration dependent i.e. with the increased concentration of test, the activity increased. The % protection of the HRBC membrane of the aqueous extract was 87.93 % and 68.06% at the dose of 400 µg/ml and 200µg/ml whereas, that of ethanolic extract was 67.91% and 71.52% at the dose of 200µg/ml and 400µg/ml respectively. Among both the extracts, aqueous extract at a concentration of 400µg/ml showed maximum (87.93 %) protection of HRBC. The results are expressed in Table 3 and Figure 2.

Table 3 Evaluation of anti-inflammatory activity by in-vitro method

S.N	EXTRACT	QUANTITY	ABSORBANCE (560nm)	%Protection Of HRBC Membrane
1.	Aqueous extract	200µg/ml	0.04567±0.001333*	68.06%
2.	Aqueous extract	400µg/ml	0.01733±0.000333*	87.93%
3.	Ethanolic extract	200µg/ml	0.08587±0.001288*	40.23%
4.	Ethanolic extract	400µg/ml	0.08200±0.000577*	42.92%
5.	Standard drug (diclofenac)	100µg/ml	0.04300±0.001732*	70.08%
6.	Standard drug (diclofenac)	200µg/ml	0.01033±0.002028*	92.83%
7.	Negative control	-	0.14367±0.000333	

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

Figure 2 The percentage (%) protection of human red blood cell membrane by ethanolic and aqueous extract of *Kalanchoe pinnata* plant and standard diclofenac used as the reference.

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to study the significance of the 3 factors (extracts, doses, and diclofenac sodium) over the variable responses for the experimental data obtained. The results obtained for various treatment combinations using ANOVA are summarized in Table 4 significant differences among all the factors and significant interactions among the evaluated levels were detected. These results show the influence of the 3 factors on the stabilization of the HRBC membrane.

Table 4 Analysis of variance (ANOVA)

Groups	Sum of Squares	Different	Mean Square	F	p-value
Between Groups	.039	6	.006	1358.319	.000
Within Groups	.000	14	.000		
Total	.039	20			

Table continued

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	p-value	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Ethanollic extract (200mcg)	Negative control	-.057800*	.001781	.000	-.06299	-.05261
Ethanollic extract (400mcg)	negative control	-.061667*	.001781	.000	-.06685	-.05648
Aqueous extract (200mcg)	negative control	-.098000*	.001781	.000	-.10319	-.09281
Aqueous extract (400mcg)	negative control	-.126333*	.001781	.000	-.13152	-.12115
Standard drug (100mcg)	negative control	-.100667*	.001781	.000	-.10585	-.09548
Standard drug (200mcg)	negative control	-.133333*	.001781	.000	-.13852	-.12815

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

a. Dunnett t-tests treat one group as a control and compare all other groups against it.

3.3 In-vivo anti-inflammatory activity

The paw edema in the control increased and reached a maximum of 3 hours after carrageenan treatment. The aqueous extracts and ethanolic extracts of *Kalanchoe pinnata* produced a statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease in the carrageenan-induced rat paw edema. Maximum inhibition of paw edema was found to be 86.38% for diclofenac 10mg/kg, 67.91% for ethanolic extract (300mg/kg), 71.52% for ethanolic extract(600mg/kg), 68.61% for aqueous extract (300mg/kg) and 83.75% for aqueous extract 600mg/kg. Among these extracts, the aqueous extract showed more inhibitory activity on inflammation. The results are expressed in Table 5 and Figure 3.

Table 5 Evaluations of Anti-inflammatory Activity

Group	Treatment Design	Dose	Paw volume in mm as measured by vernier caliper (mean±SEM)				
			0 min	30 min	60 min	120 min	180 min
I	Normal control (carrageenan)	0.1ml	3.118±0.064 76	3.178±0.064 76	3.958±0.064 76	4.198±0.064 76	4.558±0.068 95
II	Standard (Diclofenac)+ carrageenan	10mg/kg	3.036±0.046 11	3.080±0.046 90*	3.158±0.049 94*	3.248±0.046 84*	3.232±0.043 17*
III	Ethanollic extract + carrageenan	300mg/kg	2.992±0.046 75	3.146±0.046 75*	3.346±0.046 75*	3.486±0.046 75*	3.454±0.046 86*
IV	Ethanollic extract + carrageenan	600mg/kg	2.954±0.099 13	3.156±0.100 43*	3.376±0.101 47*	3.576±0.101 47*	3.364±0.097 45*
V	Aqueous extract + carrageenan	300mg/kg	3.294±0.103 32	3.512±0.106 46*	3.724±0.107 22*	3.954±0.103 32*	3.746±0.103 03*
VI	Aqueous extract + carrageenan	600mg/kg	3.568±0.119 47	3.674±0.116 60*	3.846±0.117 41*	3.822±0.118 55*	3.802±0.118 55*

P values $P < 0.05$

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

Values are expressed as mean±SEM, n=5 animals in each group

One-way ANOVA test

Figure 3 The percentage (%) inhibition of paw-edema by ethanolic and aqueous extract of *Kalanchoe pinnata* plant and standard diclofenac was used as the positive control. The paw volume of rats was measured by using the digital vernier caliper.

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to study the significance of the 3 factors (extracts, doses, and diclofenac sodium) over the variable responses for the experimental data obtained. The results obtained for various treatment combinations using ANOVA are summarized in Table 6. Significant differences among all the factors and significant interactions among the evaluated levels were detected. These results show the influence of the 3 factors on inhibition of paw-edema.

Table 6 Analysis of variance (ANOVA)

Groups		Sum of Squares	Different factor	Mean Square	F	p-value
Inflammation of volume of rats paw at 30min	Between Groups	.003	5	.001	5.726	.001
	Within Groups	.002	24	.000		
	Total	.005	29			
Inflammation volume of rats at 60 min after	Between Groups	1.399	5	.280	1311.250	.000

administration of drug and carrageenan	Within Groups	.005	24	.000		
	Total	1.404	29			
Inflammation volume of rats at 120 min after administration of drug and carrageenan	Between Groups	2.751	5	.550	7175.235	.000
	Within Groups	.002	24	.000		
	Total	2.752	29			
Inflammation volume of rats at 180 min after administration of drug and carrageenan	Between Groups	5.267	5	1.053	4158.400	.000
	Within Groups	.006	24	.000		
	Total	5.273	29			

Table continued

Dependent Variable	(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	pvalue	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Inflammation of the volume of rat paw at 30min	Normal control	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	.02000*	.00616	.015	.0034	.0366
	Standard control (diclofenac 10mg/kg)	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	-.01000	.00616	.369	-.0266	.0066
	Ethanollic extract (600mg/kg)	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	-.00200	.00616	.997	-.0186	.0146

	Ethanollic extract (300mg/kg)	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	.01000	.00616	.369	-.0066	.0266
	Aqueous extract (300mg/kg)	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	.00600	.00616	.791	-.0106	.0226
Inflammation volume of rats at 60 min after administration of drug carrageenan	Normal control	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	.52400*	.00924	.000	.4991	.5489
	Ethanollic extract (600mg/kg)	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	.01000	.00924	.720	-.0149	.0349
	Ethanollic extract (300mg/kg)	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	.10600*	.00924	.000	.0811	.1309
	Aqueous extract (300mg/kg)	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	.11400*	.00924	.000	.0891	.1389
Inflammation volume of rats at 120 min after administration of drug and carrageenan	Normal control	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	.79400*	.00554	.000	.7791	.8089
	Standard control (diclofenac 10mg/kg)	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	-.07600*	.00554	.000	-.0909	-.0611
	Ethanollic extract (600mg/kg)	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	-.00400	.00554	.921	-.0189	.0109

	Ethanollic extract (300mg/kg)	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	.33400*	.00554	.000	.3191	.3489
	Aqueous extract (300mg/kg)	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	.37200*	.00554	.000	.3571	.3869
Inflammation volume of rats at 180 min after administration of drug and carrageenan	Normal control	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	1.15600*	.01007	.000	1.1289	1.1831
	Standard control (diclofenac 10mg/kg)	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	-.07200*	.01007	.000	-.0991	-.0449
	Ethanollic extract (600mg/kg)	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	.02400	.01007	.096	-.0031	.0511
	Ethanollic extract (300mg/kg)	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	.14400*	.01007	.000	.1169	.1711
	Aqueous extract (300mg/kg)	Aqueous extract (600mg/kg)	.18000*	.01007	.000	.1529	.2071

Table Caption

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

a. Dunnett t-tests treat one group as a control and compare all other groups against it.

4. Discussion

Medicinal plants are regarded as a rich source of substances that can be employed in the creation and synthesis of drugs. Some plants are regarded as significant sources of nutrition while others are recommended for their medicinal properties¹. Various researchers have concentrated on the anti-inflammatory properties of different plants as well as the presence of secondary metabolites with pharmacological and therapeutic values. These reports have a large extended view to provide insights into the predisposing factors contributing to the efficacy of

natural plants in the management of inflammation. Generally, the potency of plants as anti-inflammatory agents is determined by the nature of the extract, the concentration of the extracts, and the presence of phytochemicals.

The phytochemical study of *Kalanchoe pinnata* revealed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, glycosides, polyphenols, tannins carbohydrate gum, and reducing sugar. The presence of this corresponded with the result of Shruti et al., (2018)³ and Pattewar (2012)¹⁷.

Our results revealed significant in-vitro anti-inflammatory activity as compared to standard. The aqueous extract showed significant anti-inflammatory activity with % protection of HRBC membrane of 87.93 % and 68.06% at the dose of 400 µg/ml and 200µg/ml whereas the ethanolic extract showed 67.91% and 71.52% at the dose of 200µg/ml and 400µg/ml respectively. Research conducted by Agrawal et al., (2019) on the anti-inflammatory activity screening of *Kalanchoe pinnata* methanol extract and its validation using a computational simulation approach showed that the methanolic extract of *Kalanchoe pinnata* has an anti-inflammatory activity due to its protective activity against human red blood cell membrane⁴³.

Kalanchoe Pinnata Pers. leaves extracts exhibited membrane stabilization effect by inhibiting hypotonicity-induced lysis of erythrocyte membrane. The erythrocyte membrane is analogous to the lysosomal membrane²¹ and its stabilization implies that the extract may as well stabilize lysosomal membranes. Stabilization of the lysosomal membrane is important in limiting the inflammatory response by preventing the release of lysosomal constituents of activated neutrophils such as bactericidal enzymes and proteases, which cause further tissue inflammation and damage upon extracellular release²². Some of the NSAIDs are known to possess membrane stabilization properties which may contribute to the potency of their anti-inflammatory effect. Though the exact mechanism of the membrane stabilization by the extract is not known yet; hypotonicity-induced hemolysis may arise from shrinkage of the cells due to osmotic loss of intracellular electrolyte and fluid components. The extract may inhibit the processes, which may stimulate or enhance the efflux of these intracellular components²³.

The percentage inhibition of paw volume 3 hours after injection of the carrageenan 1% w/v (0.1ml) was found to be 86.38%, 67.91%, 71.52%, 68.61%, and 83.75% due to diclofenac 10mg/kg, ethanolic extract 300 and 600mg/kg and aqueous extract 300 and 600mg/kg respectively. Among these two extracts, the aqueous extract showed the more inhibitory activity of inflammation. Research conducted by Mathew et al., (2013) on the analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity of *Kalanchoe pinnata* in rats showed that the aqueous and ethanolic extract of *Kalanchoe pinnata* inhibits the inflammation of paw edema induced by carrageen. The percentage inhibition of ethanolic extract of the dried stem was 34.5-36.5% and 46.62-48.03% dose at 300mg/kg and 600mg/kg respectively whereas the percentage inhibition of aqueous extract was 40.55-41.21% and 50.53-51.23% at a dose of 300mg/kg and 600mg/kg respectively which correspond to our finding¹⁵.

Prostaglandins play an important role in the setting of the cardinal signs of inflammation, pain, heat, redness, edema, and loss of function. The biosynthesis of PGE₂, the main inflammatory prostaglandin, involves three key enzymes, phospholipase A₂ (PLA₂), cyclooxygenase (COX), and PGE synthase (PGES)²⁷. Some flavonoids may reduce PGE₂ synthesis by inhibiting the activity of these enzymes or by inhibiting the expression of the inflammatory-induced enzymes, COX-2, or microsomal PGES-1^{28,29,30}. The presence of flavonoids in the plant may have been linked to producing an anti-inflammatory effect by inhibition of PG synthesis through COX inhibition.

Carrageenan is a sulfated polysaccharide of plant origin, isolated from the algae *Chondrus crispus*, and widely used as an edematogenic agent. The induction of paw edema performed with the subplantar administration of carrageenan is considered a standard model of acute local inflammation, presenting a biphasic characteristic. In the first phase, edema is mediated by the release of histamine, serotonin, and bradykinin and increased prostaglandin synthesis (between 1 h and 2 h after induction). The release of prostaglandin, platelet activation factor (PAF), substance P, proteases, cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8), and lysosomes occur in the second phase of edema (3 to 4 h after the induction)^{45,46}. According to the biphasic characteristic of the paw edema model induced by carrageenan, it can be suggested that the *K. pinnata* leaf aqueous extract can inhibit the inflammatory mediators released in the two phases whereas the *K. pinnata* leaf ethanolic extract can slightly inhibit the mediators released in the two phase. Therefore, the aqueous extract of species *K. pinnata* showed better anti-inflammatory activity in comparison to the ethanolic extract of *K. pinnata* species.

5. Conclusion and Future Prospects

Preliminary phytochemical screening of ethanolic and aqueous extracts of *K. pinnata* revealed the presence of Saponins, Alkaloids, Glycosides, Flavonoids, carbohydrates, Gum, reducing sugar, and Tannins.

The ethanolic and aqueous extracts of the leaves of *Kalanchoe pinnata* were studied for in vitro anti-inflammatory activity by the HRBC membrane stabilization method. The results revealed the dose-dependent percentage protection against HRBC membrane to prove its anti-inflammatory activity. The ethanolic and aqueous extracts of the *Kalanchoe pinnata* plant were studied for in-vivo anti-inflammatory activity and the result demonstrated that the plant possessed dose-dependent antiinflammatory activity against the carragenan-induced paw edema in rats.

Therefore, we can conclude from this study that the plant possessed potent anti-inflammatory activity which can be utilized to generate the lead molecules for the development of new anti-inflammatory drugs. Isolation of specific phytoconstituents that contribute to the potential anti-inflammatory activity can be carried out and further testing of the component on the large sample size along with clinical trials can be conducted to develop it as a novel drug effective against inflammation

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7. Conflict of interest

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. All authors approved the final manuscript.

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